
KNOWLEDGE OF KIDNEY DISEASES AMONG DOCTORS

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Abstract:

Objective: The purpose of this study is to compare the knowledge of the medical doctors and trainee doctors of post graduate studies performing their duties in department of nephrology or other departments.

Methodology: This transverse case work carried out at the department of nephrology in Mayo Hospital Lahore. The duration of this research work was from 1st April 2019 to April 30, 2019. The doctors who were performing their duties in the hospital having more than one-year experience after the completion of their house job were the part of this research work. Every doctor has to fill a questionnaire consisting twenty-eight questions.

Results: Total 211 doctors according to the standard of the work were the members of this research work. Majority of the participants of this research work were male doctors 71.10% (n: 150). There was strong association of the knowledge with practice of doctor. The knowledge about the different kidney diseases was different among the medical professional of various hospitals. The practice about the kidney diseases was also different among the doctors of different hospitals. The doctors of Mayo Hospital Lahore were available with the highest scores of the awareness and knowledge about these diseases.

Conclusion: The knowledge of the medical officers as well as postgraduate trainee doctors is not well enough about the diseases of kidney. The doctors who were working in the department off nephrology are available with better knowledge as compared to the doctors working in other departments. The experience and the practice of the doctors was improving the awareness and knowledge of these diseases among doctors.

KEY WORDS: Kidney, Practice, Diseases, Awareness, Professionals, Postgraduate, Trainee, Departments.

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INTRODUCTION:

Nephrology is a special field which only handles the kidney diseases. In our country Pakistan, the first nephrologist was professor SA Jaffar Naqvi who entered in Jinnah Medical Hospital, located in Karachi in the year of 1970 [1]. After that, in 1980’s training of nephrology initiated in College of Physicians & Surgeons of Pakistan in 3 big cities of our country as Lahore, Peshawar and Karachi. At the end of 2000, there were total twelve centers of nephrology were available for postgraduate studies in our country. From last few years, there is great advancement in these centers and now a day, there are more than twenty-eight centers of nephrology are available in our country [2]. There are total eighty professional nephrologists in our country for a huge population in comparison with the USA which as more than five thousand specialists for their populations [3].

The undeveloped field of nephrology is the cause of bad training & inadequate teaching. This results into the deficiency of the knowledge in the diagnosis & administration of the diseases of kidney among the doctors [4]. Knowledge deficiency about the guidelines of medical practice and the referral of the patients of the diseases of kidney at last stages to the specialists enhances the morbidity as well as mortality of these patients [5, 6]. The training of the doctors from the well developed countries is not satisfactory [7, 8]. There is very less information available in our country about the practice and awareness about the diseases of kidney among medical officers and trainees. But we found no research work on this subject. Therefore, this research work conducted to find out the disparity of awareness and practice between the doctors performing their duties in department of nephrology and other departments.

METHODOLOGY:

This transverse research work carried out in 8 big hospitals of Lahore but the center of the study was Mayo Hospital, Lahore. Doctors performing their duties in different departments from greater than one-year duration were the part of this research work. The evaluation of the medical officers & doctors of postgraduate studies conducted in this case work. The doctors having other specialization or nephrology were not the part of this research work. Every doctor filled a questionnaire which was consisting twenty-eight questions. There were 3 parts of the questionnaire which were covering awareness, attitude & practice of the doctors about the diseases of kidney. The theme of the questionnaire was covering the all general information about the diseases of kidney. The identification of the doctors was under cover and every doctor filled questionnaire in ten to fifteen minutes on the spot.

SPSS V.17 was in use for the analysis of the information. Averages ± SD values were in use for the expression of the continuous values. The signification of the variables carried out with the help of ANOVA. P value of less than 0.050 was significant. We used the correlation to find out the relation among various variables.

RESULTS

Total 211 who were completing the requirements of the case study. The amount of doctors of various hospitals is available in Table-1. The majority of the doctors were from military hospital. Male doctors were in large quantity as 71.10% (n: 150). The female doctors were 28.90% (n: 61). The average experience of the doctors after MBBS was twenty-nine weeks with arrange of 1-120 weeks. There was very positive correlation of Knowledge with the experience whereas there was no association among knowledge and attitude and attitude and practice.

Table-I: Number of the doctors from different hospitals.

Name of Institute	No	Percent
Mayo Hospital (MH)	42.0	20.00
Jinnah Hospital (JH)	31.0	14.00
Services Institute of Medical Sciences (SIMS)	27.0	13.00
Shaikh Zayed Hospital (SZH)	25.0	12.00
Sir Ganga Ram Hospital (SGRH)	25.0	12.00
Lahore General Hospital (LGH)	25.0	12.00
Shalamar Hospital (SH)	19.0	9.00
Fatima Memorial Hospital (FMH)	17.0	8.00

The awareness and practice about the kidney diseases was very different among doctors of various health care institutes. The maximum knowledge according to the performance of the doctors in questionnaire was available in the doctors of Mayo Hospital Lahore, about the diseases of kidney as compared to the doctors of the other hospitals as available in Figure-1 and Figure-2.

Fig.1: Graph showing mean knowledge score of doctors working at different hospitals of Lahore

Fig.2: Graph showing mean practice score of doctors working at different hospitals of Lahore

The attitude components were large in the doctors of SH in comparison with all other hospitals of Lahore as described in as displayed in Figure-3. The experience of working & score of practice about the kidney diseases was available with very important association but attitude and awareness do not have such correlation.

Fig.3: Graph showing mean attitude score of doctors working at different hospitals of Lahore

DISCUSSION:

The incidence of the kidney diseases is one hundred and fifty million patients every year [9]. In accordance with a research work of Jafar TH, from 15% to 20% people with forty year of age or above have a reduced infection of kidney [10]. In accordance with the national health research, about one third people of Pakistan above the age of forty-five years were hypertensive [11]. In our country Pakistan, the system of health is not up to the mark and only four of GDP has allocated for health facilities [12]. The diseases which are spreading with the increase of the populations are not under focus particularly kidney diseases which are spreading with the passage of time. The services of nephrology are in their initial stages of advancement in only the teaching hospitals. There is no availability of the specialists in this field so patients have to travel a long distance to consult the doctors of this particular field which can cause the aggravation of the situation. The maximum knowledge was available about the kidney diseases among doctors of Mayo Hospital Lahore in comparison with all the other hospitals of Lahore. The goof awareness and scores of practice displays the benefits of well established department of nephrology in comparison with the other hospitals where the department of nephrology are in their stage of infancy. Five hospitals are providing the post graduate in this particular field from last 3 to 4 years in the city of Lahore. But we found no benefits of their presence because they are only under the stage of development with deficiency of facilities. This is the responsibility of government to provide full facilities to such departments to decrease the mortality & morbidity due to the kidney diseases. In this research work, there is a strong correlation between practice and knowledge. This provided correlation was also the result of various research works [13]. By educating and enhancing the knowledge of the doctors about the referral of the patients to nephrologists in initial stages will decrease the mortality as well as morbidity of the patients suffering from the kidney diseases [14, 15]. The knowledge of the doctors was increasing day by day with the increase of their experience and practice.

CONCLUSION

The awareness of the doctors was not up to the mark about diseases of kidney in this research work. The doctors who were working in the departments of nephrology found with good knowledge about these diseases as compared to the doctors working in other departments. The strong correlation was available between knowledge and practice. The experience of working was improving the knowledge of the doctors. There is a great requirement of making the departments of nephrology in all teaching hospitals.

The medicine of kidney diseases should be a subject in the graduation of the doctors. There should be regular study programs on the kidney diseases.

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